

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Overview of existing data for use in SPRINT WP6

Peter Fantke (DTU)

Milestone number: 9

Milestone title: Collection of existing data for use in WP6 completed

Lead beneficiary: 11 - DTU

Due date: 31-08-2021 (month 12)

Publishing date: 31-08-2021

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Title	Sustainable Plant Protection Transition; A global health approach
Project Acronym	SPRINT
Call Identifier	H2020-SFS-2019-2; Sustainable Food Security
Grant Agreement no.	862568
Starting Date	01-09-2020
End Date	31-08-2025
Project duration	60 months
Website address	www.sprint-h2020.eu
Overall Project coordinator	Prof. Dr. V. GEISSEN (violette.geissen@wur.nl)
Scientific coordinator	Prof. Dr. P. SCHEEPERS (paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl)
EU project officer	Bela ATZEL

REPORT INFORMATION

Report Title	Overview of existing data for use in SPRINT WP6
Milestone Number	9
Milestone Title	Collection of existing data for use in WP6 completed
Means of verification	Collection of existing data for use in WP6 completed
Related Work Package	6
Author(s) of report (institution)	Peter Fantke (DTU), Marissa Kosnik (DTU), Jennifer Mark (FiBL), Christian Grovermann (FiBL), Lucius Tamm (FiBL)
Principle Author e-mail	pefan@dtu.dk
Editor(s)	Lucius Tamm (FiBL)
E--Mail(s)	lucius.tamm@fibl.org
Milestone Due Date	31-08-2021 (month 12)
Milestone publish date	31-08-2021

Contents

Contents	3
1 Summary	4
2 Overview of data collected and their data sources	4
2.1 Pesticide physicochemical properties	4
2.1.1 EFSA reports and databases	4
2.1.2 ECHA REACH database	5
2.1.3 US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard	6
2.2 Case study site data availability	7
2.3 Application scenarios data	7
2.3.1 SPRINT case study site application scenarios	8
2.3.2 Farm accountancy data network (FADN)	9
2.3.3 Regional and national agronomic management practices application data	9
2.3.4 National pesticide application data	9
3 Data collection methods	10
3.1 Pesticide physicochemical properties	11
3.1.1 EFSA	11
3.1.2 REACH	11
3.1.3 US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard	12
3.2 Application scenarios data	12
3.2.1 Case study site application scenarios	12
3.2.2 FADN	13
3.2.3 National pesticide use statistics	13
4 Use of data (links to tasks, analyses, outcomes)	14
4.1.1 Overview of data use in WP6 tasks	14
4.1.2 Pesticide emission consensus model data formats	14
4.1.3 USEtox model data formats	16
4.1.4 dynamiCROP model data formats	18
4.1.5 Economic data/models	20
5 Data storage and data protection	22
6 References	22

1 Summary

Different types of existing data have been successfully collected from various data sources for use in WP6 tasks. These data cover different features of pesticides and scenarios for their use. An overview of these data is provided below, and includes the data sources, example data, a summary on data collection methods, in which tasks the data are used, and information on storage and protection of the data. According to the present milestone, all WP6 expected objectives will be fully reached based on the collected existing data. Additional data collection might lead to further results refinement, where appropriate.

2 Overview of data collected and their data sources

2.1 Pesticide physicochemical properties

Data for various types of pesticides will be collected and used. These include organic pesticides (e.g. carbamates) and inorganic pesticides (e.g. copper-based fungicides) that are approved in the European Union and/or used in the project case studies as active ingredients of various plant protection product formulations for use in agriculture.

These data were integrated across three main data sources: European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) risk assessment reports and databases (e.g. OpenFoodTox, Pesticide Properties Database - PPDB), dossiers submitted under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals Regulation (REACH) regulation, and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US-EPA) Chemistry Dashboard database. Additional data sources are also described. Data quality will be checked across sources, with preference given on already curated data in the different sources. Data gaps will be complemented by a hierarchy of different sources (e.g. publications of curated species sensitivity distributions for >12000 chemicals from the EU SOLUTIONS project).

2.1.1 EFSA reports and databases

Information on individual substances with a summary of human health, animal health, and ecological hazard assessment results are contained in the chemical hazards database. These data cover 5500 chemical substances, including over 1250 pesticides.

Data that will be used from this data source include:

- Different points of departure for human toxicity characterization (e.g. BMDL, NOAEL) derived from different human or animal test studies, including related information on test species, exposure test duration, tested health endpoint if available)
- Different ecological toxicity data for freshwater ecotoxicity characterization (e.g. NOEC, EC50) for all freshwater aquatic species with available data, including related information on test species, exposure test duration, tested endpoint if available)
- Uncertainty factors

An overview of these data through the web-interface is shown in Figure 1. These data can be accessed on the web through <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/data/chemical-hazards-data>. More information about these data can be found in the OpenFoodTox scientific articles (Dorne et al., 2017; Dorne et al., 2021). Additionally, individual pesticide reports can be

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

found within the EFSA journal for all approved European pesticides (e.g., cypermethrin (Arena et al., 2018)).

Please, use one search field at a time and click on "Apply". If more than one filter is used, the tool will intersect all searched data. If you wish to see the alternative names (synonyms) of a substance please, select the substance name in the Substance characterisation table.

Substance Characterisation							Synonym
Substance	has	Component	CAS number	EC Ref No	Molecular formula	Smiles	Synonym
(-)-3,7-Dimethyl-6-octen-1-ol	as such	(-)-3,7-Dimethyl-6-octen-1-ol	7540-51-4	211-415-7	C10H20O		2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane Bisphenol A
(-)-Alpha-cedrene	as such	(-)-Alpha-cedrene	469-61-4	207-712-2	C15H24	CC1=CCC2C(C@H)1C(C)(C)C@H2C(C@H)2C	BPA

EFSA outputs							
Substance	Author	Published	Output Id	Title	Output Type	Legal Basis	Url
1-[4-Methoxyphenyl]-4-methylpent-1-en-3-ol	EFSA FAF	11/11/2019	3348	Scientific Opinion on Flavouring Group Evaluation 215 Revision 1 (FGE.215Rev1): seven a,b-unsaturated cinnamyl ketones from subgroup 3.2 of FGE.15	EFSA opinion	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1565/2008 (Repealed by Commission Reg. (EU) No 872/2012)	http://dx.doi.org/10.2903/efsa.2019.5875
1-[4-Methoxyphenyl]pent-1-en-3-ol	EFSA FAF	11/11/2019	3348	Scientific Opinion on Flavouring Group Evaluation 215 Revision 1 (FGE.215Rev1): seven a,b-unsaturated cinnamyl ketones from subgroup 3.2 of FGE.15	EFSA opinion	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1565/2008 (Repealed by Commission Reg. (EU) No 872/2012)	http://dx.doi.org/10.2903/efsa.2019.5875
3-Methyl-4-phenylbut-3-en-2-one	EFSA FAF	11/11/2019	3348	Scientific Opinion on Flavouring Group Evaluation 215 Revision 1 (FGE.215Rev1): seven a,b-unsaturated cinnamyl ketones from subgroup 3.2 of FGE.15	EFSA opinion	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1565/2008 (Repealed by Commission Reg. (EU) No 872/2012)	http://dx.doi.org/10.2903/efsa.2019.5875

Hazard Characterisation: Reference points														
Substance	Author	Year	Output Id	Study	Test Type	Species	Route	Duration (days)	Endpoint	Qualifier	Value	Unit	Effect	Toxicity
(-)-Myosamine and (-)-Scopolamine group	EFSA CORTAM	2013	2396	Animal (target species) health	not reported	Pig	Not reported	0	NOAEL	=	1500	µg/kg bw	not reported	not reported
(-)-Myosamine and (-)-Scopolamine group	EFSA CORTAM	2013	2396	Human health	study with volunteers	Human	Not reported	0	NOAEL	=	0.16	µg/kg bw	clinical signs	systemic
(1R,2S,5R)-N-[(2-(Pyridine-2-yl)ethyl)-3-p-menthane-carboxamide	EFSA CEF	2014	2524	Human health	subchronic	Rat	oral; feed	90	NOAEL	=	5	mg/kg bw/day	histopathology	endocrine
(1R,2S,5R)-N-[(Ethoxycarbonyl)methyl]-p-menthane-3-carboxamide	EFSA CEF	2012	2134	Human health	subchronic	Rat	oral; gavage	90	NOAEL	=	75	mg/kg bw/day	not neoplastic	systemic
(1R,2S,5R)-N-[(Ethoxycarbonyl)methyl]-p-menthane-3-carboxamide	EFSA CEF	2014	2481	Human health	subchronic	Rat	oral; gavage	90	NOAEL	=	75	mg/kg bw/day	haematology	systemic
110-10-10; 10-10-10; 10-10-10; 10-10-10; 10-10-10; 10-10-10	EFSA	2015	3145	Human health	subchronic	Rat	oral; feed	90	NOAEL	=	1.00	mg/kg bw/day	not reported	haematotoxicity

Hazard Characterisation: Reference values													
Substance	Author	Year	Output Id	Assessment	Qualifier	Value	Unit	Population	Remarks				
(-)-3,7-Dimethyl-6-octen-1-ol	EFSA CEF	2013	2180	TTC Cramer Class 1	=	30	µg/kg bw/day	Consumers	METABOLISM: The candidate substance is expected to be metabolised to innocuous products at the estimated levels of use as flavouring substances in this group the data available do not give rise to safety concern with respect to genotoxicity and carcinogenicity. OUTCOME: safety concern based on intake calculated by the MSDI approach of the named compound. OUTCOME ON THE MATERIAL OF COMMERCE level of intake of the material of commerce meeting the specification (based on intake calculated by the MSDI approach).				

Genotoxicity				
Substance	Author	Year	Output Id	Genotoxicity
(-)-3,7-Dimethyl-6-octen-1-ol	EFSA CEF	2013	2180	Negative
(-)-3,7-Dimethyl-6-octen-1-ol	EFSA FEEDAP	2016	2864	Not determined
(-)-Alpha-cedrene	EFSA AFC	2008	2299	Not determined
(-)-Alpha-cedrene	EFSA CEF	2010	2039	Not determined
(-)-Alpha-cedrene	EFSA CEF	2011	2102	Not determined
(-)-Alpha-elelol	EFSA AFC	2006	2232	Negative
(-)-Alpha-elelol	EFSA AFC	2009	2314	Negative
(-)-Alpha-elelol	EFSA CEF	2011	2071	Negative
(-)-Alpha-elelol	EFSA CEF	2015	2656	Negative
(-)-Alpha-Santalene	EFSA AFC	2008	2299	Not determined

Figure 1. Overview of EFSA chemical hazards database.

2.1.2 ECHA REACH database

Parameters that are not available in EFSA's database or data for chemicals not included in the EFSA database will be collected from ECHA's REACH database.

Atrazine

EC number: 217-617-8 | CAS number: 1912-24-9

General information

- Classification & Labelling & PBT assessment
- Manufacture, use & exposure
- Physical & Chemical properties
- Environmental fate & pathways
- Ecotoxicological information
- Toxicological information
- Analytical methods
- Guidance on safe use
- Assessment reports

Substance identity

Identification Type of substance Substance identifiers Compositions

Identification

Display Name: Atrazine

EC Number: 217-617-8

EC Name: Atrazine

CAS Number: 1912-24-9

Molecular formula: C8H14ClN5

IUPAC Name: 6-chloro-N2-ethyl-N4-(propan-2-yl)-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine

Type of Substance

Composition: mono-constituent substance

Origin: organic

Substance Identifiers

Figure 2. Example REACH registration dossier landing page.

REACH establishes

procedures to curate chemical property and hazard information. These data are housed in the REACH Registered substances portal, which contains information from REACH registration dossiers provided by substance manufacturers and importers. These collected data describe the chemical registration (date of last update, whether or not the registration is active), the tonnage of manufactured substance, and product use and exposure information, including environmental release categories (e.g., industrial use, wide dispersive indoor use, etc.). A sample landing page for a chemical search is shown in Figure 2. However, this database contains pesticide information only to the extent that they are also used as industrial chemicals.

Among these data, the following information will be used (see also Fantke et al. (2020)):

- Hazard classification (including physical, health, and environmental)
- Manufacture, use, and exposure information
- Physical and chemical properties (including melting/boiling point, solubility, pH, etc.)
- Environmental fate and pathway information (including biodegradation, bioaccumulation, transport and distribution, etc.)
- Ecotoxicological information (see previous section for EFSA database for details)
- And general toxicological information (oral, inhalation, dermal, acute, chronic, etc.)

These data cover 23219 unique substances with information from 102884 dossiers. These data can be accessed through <https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals/registered-substances>. Additional information on these data can be found through REACH FAQs and general information: <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/understanding-reach>.

2.1.3 US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard

Information that is not available in either EFSA or ECHA databases will be derived from additional data sources, mainly from the US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard.

Figure 3. Sample landing page for CompTox Chemistry Dashboard.

The US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard is a resource maintained by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and is a web-based tool integrating cheminformatics data, including measured and predicted physicochemical properties, environmental fate and transport data, and exposure and toxicity data. These data are collected from human biomonitoring, in vivo experiments, and high-throughput in vitro chemical testing. These

data are also generated using quantitative structure activity relationships, exposure models, and Bayesian methods, to compile a set of data for the purpose or regulatory application in the United States. These data can be accessed through the web resource: <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard>. A sample landing page for a chemical is shown in Figure 3.

This repository integrates data across resources, including from aggregated public data like ACToR, consumer products and categories functional use data (CPDat), summarized in vivo data (ToxValDB), in vitro assay data (inVitroDB), and experimental and predicted chemical properties data.

In brief, these data include:

- Chemical properties (including experimental and predicted ranges)
- Environmental fate and transport data
- Chemical hazard data
- Chemical exposure data (both from biomonitoring and prediction models)
- Chemical bioactivity data (covering >1000 chemical assays)
- And chemical use (e.g., in consumer products)

More details on these data and integrated data repositories are available in the latest CompTox Chemistry Dashboard publication (Williams et al., 2017).

2.2 Case study site data availability

Sampling and data collection just finished in most CSS and data is now being translated back to English. In some cases, questionnaires might not be sent back or translated on time for further processing. If such cases should occur, several options are conceivable:

- WP6 will have a closer interaction with CSS leaders to ensure that questionnaires are becoming available before actual data are needed for simulations. As planned, some information won't be available before the end of the crop season and two CSS have a seasonal shift compared to other countries. In that way we are aware of possible delay in getting the data.
- Regular WP/CSS Leader meeting informs us about possible issues and current updates about questionnaire status.
- We aim at implementing certain extrapolation (or interpolation) methods when relevant environmental and/or economic data in questionnaires are missing.
- We aim at picking out missing data regarding agronomic management practice from agronomic leaflets, farmer journals and seasonal advices for farmers.

2.3 Application scenarios data

Application scenarios data cover specific instances of pesticide use in Europe. Such data are primarily collected at farm level via the SPRINT case study sites using dedicated questionnaires. Data include number and date of application of each PPP, application rates, way and methods of application, active ingredients. Complementary to SPRINT-internal data, data are required from other farms in Europe to enable comparison, and scale-up to different spatial levels. Such complementary data include data from the AgroWin application scenarios database. An overview of these data is presented below.

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

2.3.1 SPRINT case study site application scenarios

Application scenarios data collected via case study sites (see Figure 4) cover agronomic management practices from a large range of crops across 11 countries. Such data are collected using a specific questionnaire filled in by case study site leaders and covering all activities done by the farmer on a given field and crop starting at pre-sowing activities to harvest activities.

Figure 4. SPRINT Case Study Sites (CSS) location, crops and livestock. Blue on the map = Northern Europe, Green = Central Europe, Red = Southern Europe. Italian and French CSS have no livestock. CSS 2 (Portugal) and CSS 9 (Netherlands) are reference CSS for modelling.

Among these data are:

- Farm characterization data: type of farming system (C-I-O), number of fields and surroundings of these fields, crops, machineries, infrastructures
- Crop characterization data: coordinates of field, crop rotation, soil characterization, open question about pesticide application decisions
- Crop log book: details about pre-sowing, sowing, crop development, harvest activities

- Pesticide record: date of application, type of product, active ingredient, application rates, application methods
- Fertilizer record: date of fertilization, type of fertilization
- Costs and benefits: revenues, variable costs, labor, fixed costs machinery

2.3.2 Farm accountancy data network (FADN)

The farm accountancy data network (FADN) monitors farms' income and business activities. It is the only source of microeconomic data in the EU based on harmonised bookkeeping. The dataset is based on national surveys and covers only EU agricultural holdings which due to their size can be considered commercial. The microdata (farm-level) contains information on several 10,000 farms across all member states. It is an important informative source for understanding the economics of farm management and the impact of policy measures.

The methodology applied under FADN aims to provide representative data according to three categories: region, economic size and type of farming. It can thus complement the analysis of the case study data.

The FADN sampling procedure is illustrated in Figure 5.

For details see https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rca/methodology3_en.cfm.

Figure 5: FADN Sampling Procedure (Source: https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/rca/methodology3_en.cfm)

2.3.3 Regional and national agronomic management practices application data

Additional agronomic management practices data will be collected from regional and national agronomy leaflets published by agronomic organizations to advice farmers on technical crop management. Type of data are:

- Disease and pest management
- Fertilization management
- Technical advice on crop management

2.3.4 National pesticide application data

Individual countries report pesticide data on their respective environmental protection agency, chemical agency, and/or statistics agency's web resources. Such data, along with

recommended

application doses published in e.g. Farmer Guidelines, will be used to derive pesticide use data. Among these data are:

- Active ingredient used
- Pesticide product
- Crop(s) pesticides are used on
- Dose per active substance used

Additionally, some resources contained:

- Quantity (kg) of active ingredient used
- Hectares crop treated
- Region of crop growth/pesticide treatment

For example, the Danish Environmental Protection Agency, Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark (<https://eng.mst.dk>) reports annual land use in conventional agriculture with the total area grown by farmers reported in 1000 ha. Additionally, the standard dose (grams active substance per hectare) of active ingredients used per crop are reported. Statistics Estonia (<https://www.stat.ee/en>) also has detailed data, with the quantity of active ingredients used and basic area treated in agricultural holdings reported by crop, and crop growth per county in Estonia reported.

A sample of these data for Estonia is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample of integrated Statistics Estonia pesticide-crop application data for 2015.

County	Pest_Group	Active_Ingredient	Crop	Area_Treated_ha	AI_Quantity_kg
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	Cereals	1582.78	384
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	spring crops	1427.42	354.54
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	barley	1160.01	160.82
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	spring wheat	267.41	193.72
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	winter crops	155.36	29.46
Harju	Fungicides	azoxystrobin	winter wheat	155.36	29.46
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	Cereals	26481.13	1264.16
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	spring crops	12967.36	658.55
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	barley	5249.71	271.01
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	spring wheat	7717.65	387.54
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	triticale	655.08	29.24
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	winter crops	13513.77	605.61
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	rye	573.62	25.52
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	winter barley	45.98	1.97
Harju	Fungicides	bixafen	winter wheat	12239.09	548.88

3 Data collection methods

Existing data were collected using standard data curation techniques. The specific approaches used for each data resource are outlined below.

3.1 Pesticide physicochemical properties

Pesticide physicochemical properties data were collected using readily available data downloads from each resource. These downloads can be found at the included web links, shared in each sub-section below.

3.1.1 EFSA

EFSA's chemical hazards data are stored in the OpenFoodTox database. The full dataset is available in XLS format, providing for all compounds: a) substance characterisation, b) EFSA outputs, c) reference points, d) reference values and, e) genotoxicity from the following link: <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/openfoodtox-efsa-s-chemical-hazards-database?locale=en>. These data were collected in bulk from the link using the provided "Download full database" feature.

3.1.2 REACH

View all Registered Substances Search Clear all

All substances Registrants/Suppliers

Page 1 of 516 50 Items per Page Showing 1 - 50 of 25,878 results. -- First Previous Next Last --

Name	EC / List no.	CAS no.	Registration Status	Registration type	Submission type	Total tonnage band	Last Updated	Details
"amyl nitrite", mixed isomers	203-770-8	463-04-7	Active	Full		≥ 10 to < 100 tonnes	28-06-2019	
"amyl nitrite", mixed isomers	203-770-8	463-04-7	Active	Intermediate		Intermediate use only	10-12-2019	
(4-hydroxystyrene, 4-t butoxy styrene and 2,5-dimethyl-2,5-diacryloxyhexane) copolymer	433-610-4	-	Active	NONS		Tonnage data confidential	10-11-2008	

Figure 6. Overview of the REACH web interface for data download.

REACH data are provided through the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) IUCLID system. These data can be searched and filtered to select specific product categories, tonnage bands of use, or exposure scenarios. By using an advanced search feature, these data can be further filtered based on properties of concern or biocide related information. Figure 6 gives an overview of the web interface for data download provided at the following link: <https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>. The relevant REACH data were collected for chemicals by using these filters to collect REACH data, and selecting "Export search results to XLS".

3.1.3 US-EPA Chemistry Dashboard

The US-EPA Chemicals Dashboard contains a "Batch Search" function to enable extraction of large datasets from the web resource. This feature is available at this link: https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/dsstoxdb/batch_search. A demonstration of the interface is provided in Figure 7.

Through this batch search function, the repository can be filtered to curate specific chemicals based on identifier and/or presence in specific lists or categories (e.g., presence in the U.S. EPA's dataset on PESTICIDES from the Office of Pesticide Programs Information Network). These filtered data were output in an XLS format for further use. Where appropriate, additional data for individual pesticides have been obtained via the regular web-frontend of the dashboard, which provides summaries of data per chemical.

Figure 7. Overview of the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard "Batch Search" feature.

3.2 Application scenarios data

As the application scenarios data were not available through web resources, they were collected through different approaches. These methods are outlined below.

3.2.1 Case study site application scenarios

Application scenario data collected via case study sites are collected by case study site leaders at each case study site including up to 20 analysed fields. Data are collected via a questionnaire designed by WP6 (Appendix_3_SPRINT_Monitoring_General_Info_WP2-WP6) and filled in by CSSL and co-workers. CSSL will have a face to face or phone exchange with farmers to fill in the questionnaire. Data will be collected at the beginning of crop season and a second time after the harvest, at the end of the crop season.

3.2.2 FADN

As only aggregated FADN data are accessible online, FADN microdata were requested via an official application process (by e-mail) from the European Commission. 283 variables (out of 300 variables at maximum) were selected to cover economic parameters and farm characteristics related to the focus crops of the project. The application is in process and data are expected to be available in autumn 2021. An example set of selected FADN variables is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Examples of variables selected from the FADN dataset

y	SE285	Seeds and plants	in EUR
y	SE290	Seeds and plants home-grown	Include the feed home-grown in DE in 2005
y	SE295	Fertilisers	in EUR
y	SE296	Fertiliser. Quantity of N in mineral fertilisers used	in q
y	SE297	Fertiliser. Quantity of P2O5 in mineral fertilisers used	in q
y	SE298	Fertiliser. Quantity of K2O in mineral fertilisers used	in q
y	SE300	Crop protection	in EUR
y	SE305	Other crop specific costs	in EUR

3.2.3 National pesticide use statistics

Lists of sources of pesticide data for each country are available from individual reports of national metadata compiled to develop Eurostat pesticide sales statistics available at the following link:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/aei_fm_salpest09_esms.htm.

Additionally, a list of registered plant protection data sources for countries are available: https://www.eppo.int/ACTIVITIES/plant_protection_products/registered_products.

To prepare data for the needed countries, relevant data were collected from each country's resource. For example, the Danish Environmental Protection Agency has pesticide statistics available in PDFs for the years 1991-2018 (<https://eng.mst.dk/chemicals/pesticides/pesticides-statistics/agriculture-etc/>). These data were extracted from the PDFs to prepare XLS tables (e.g., for the 2017 report, the relevant crop growth data are available in report Tables 4.1 and 4.2, and relevant pesticide application data are available in report Table B.2.1).

Other countries have data readily available as downloadable XLS files from their websites. For example, Estonia has "USE OF PESTICIDES IN AGRICULTURAL HOLDINGS BY COUNTY AND CROP" data available in a Table KK2082 and "QUANTITY OF PESTICIDES USED AND THE BASIC AREA TREATED IN AGRICULTURAL HOLDINGS BY ACTIVE SUBSTANCE AND CROP" data available in a Table KK2081. These data were downloaded directly from the Statistics Estonia Statistical database resource as XLS files (<https://andmed.stat.ee/en/stat>).

4 Use of data (links to tasks, analyses, outcomes)

4.1.1 Overview of data use in WP6 tasks

Existing pesticide physicochemical property as well as pesticide application scenario data will be used in WP6 across all 5 tasks. While pesticide physicochemical properties including bioaccumulation, plant uptake and toxicity/ecotoxicity data will be mainly used in the environmental sustainability assessment components of tasks 6.1 to 6.5, pesticide application scenario data will be used for both the environmental as well as the economic evaluation components across tasks 6.1 to 6.5. For integration and interoperability of environmental and economic evaluation components of the different WP6 tasks, no additional existing data will be required, but rather an alignment in terms of e.g. defining common assessment system boundary conditions, metrics and units.

In order to facilitate an operational data exchange from different data sources for use in the models applied in WP6 tasks, it is important to understand the technical requirements of data formats, which we describe in the following. Models applied in the various environmental evaluation component of WP6 tasks are PestLCI for assessing chemical emissions into the environment from applied pesticide mass (Dijkman et al., 2012; Renaud-Gentié et al., 2015; Gentil et al., 2020), the global scientific consensus model USEtox for assessing human toxicity and ecotoxicity impacts from pesticide emissions (Rosenbaum et al., 2008; Henderson et al., 2011; Rosenbaum et al., 2011; Fantke et al., 2021), and the dynamiCROP model for assessing plant uptake of pesticides and related human exposure and human health impacts (Fantke et al., 2011a; Fantke et al., 2011b; Fantke and Jolliet, 2016).

Impacts of farming scenarios (organic vs. conventional) will be systematically evaluated across the EU using representative FADN farm-level data, possibly integrating other data sources on pesticide risk. Instrumental variable regression reweighting methods are used to correct for selection effects and obtain unbiased impact estimates (Grovermann et al., in prep.).

Impacts of pesticide reduction strategies will be assessed ex-ante using an agent-based optimization model that simulates the behavior of farm agents (Grovermann et al., 2017). The model will be parameterized for specific scenarios using the data from questionnaires along with FADN data and relevant data available in the project WPs 2-4. Indicators on pesticide impacts should be integrated to allow for a comprehensive economic-ecological trade-off and synergy analysis.

Data requirements for all models are described below.

4.1.2 Pesticide emission consensus model data formats

In Table 3 and Table 4, an overview of the input data format requirements of the pesticide emission consensus model is given that is used in the environmental evaluation component of tasks 6.1 to 6.5 to assess chemical emissions into the environment from applied pesticide mass. Further information and supporting references can be found at <https://tinyurl.com/PestLCI>.

Table 3. Primary and secondary emission input data for PestLCI

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Type
Primary inputs			
Chemical abstract service registry number	Cas_number_selection	-	TEXT
Chemical common name	Name	-	TEXT
Crop type selection	Crop_type	-	TEXT
Fraction intercepted by leaf	F_intercept_leaf	mass%	FLOAT
Soil selection	Soil_Selection	-	TEXT
Climate selection	Climate_selection	-	TEXT
Month selection	Month_selection	-	TEXT
Secondary inputs – Application Technique			
Application method	Application_method	-	TEXT
Drift reduction?	Drift_reduction	-	TEXT
Application rate	Application_rate	kg/ha	FLOAT
Secondary inputs – No-spray buffer zone characteristics			
Bufferzone in technosphere?	Bz_tech	-	TEXT
Bufferzone width	Bz_width	m	FLOAT
Fraction deposited on leaves	F_intercept_buffer	-	FLOAT
Secondary inputs – Field characteristics			
Field width	Field_width	m	FLOAT
Field length	Field_length	m	FLOAT
Slope	Slope	%	FLOAT
Drainage depth	Depth_of_drainage_sy	m	FLOAT
Fraction drained	Fraction_drained	-	FLOAT
Annual irrigation	Irrigation	mm	
Tillage type	Tillage_type		TEXT
Model default parameters			
Soil material density	Solid_material_densi	kg/l	FLOAT
Fraction macropores	Fraction_macropores		FLOAT
Reference soil moisture content	Reference_soil_moist	-	FLOAT
Response factor biodegradation rate	Response_factor1	-	FLOAT
Q-value	Q_value_	-	FLOAT
Air boundary layer	Air_boundary_layer	m	FLOAT
D(lam)	D_lam	m	FLOAT
A(p,ref)	A_p_ref	kg/m ²	FLOAT

Table 4. Pesticide properties input data for PestLCI

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Type
Chemical abstract service registry number	CAS RN	-	TEXT
Substance name	Name	-	TEXT
Target class for pesticides	PesticideTargetClass	-	TEXT
Chemical class for pesticides	PesticideChemClass	-	TEXT
Molar weight	MW	g/mol	FLOAT
pKa chemical class	pKaChemClass	-	FLOAT
pKa base reaction	pKa base	-	FLOAT
pKa acid reaction	pKa acid	-	FLOAT
Partitioning coefficient between n-octanol and water	Log KOW	-	FLOAT
Partitioning coefficient between organic carbon and water	KOC	l/kg	FLOAT
Dissipation half-life in soil	DT50 soil	d	FLOAT
Saturation Vapor pressure (at 25°C)	Vapour pressure	Pa	FLOAT
Water Solubility (at 20°C)	Solubility	g/l	FLOAT

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Type
DT50 leaf - pooideae	DT50 leaf - pooideae	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - panicoideae	DT50 leaf - panicoideae	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - paddy rice	DT50 leaf - paddy rice	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - pulses	DT50 leaf - pulses	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - roots and tubers	DT50 leaf - roots and tubers	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - oil-bearing crops	DT50 leaf - oil-bearing crops	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - vegetables leafy	DT50 leaf - vegetables leafy	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - vegetables fruit	DT50 leaf - vegetables fruit	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - fruits tropical	DT50 leaf - fruits tropical	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - fruits temperate	DT50 leaf - fruits temperate	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - citrus fruits	DT50 leaf - citrus fruits	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - grapes/vines	DT50 leaf - grapes/vines	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - berries	DT50 leaf - berries	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - nuts	DT50 leaf - nuts	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - oil-bearing trees	DT50 leaf - oil-bearing trees	d	FLOAT
DT50 leaf - other permanent crops	DT50 leaf - other permanent crops	d	FLOAT

4.1.3 USEtox model data formats

In Table 5 and Table 6, an overview of the input data format requirements of the USEtox 2.0 model is given that is used in the environmental evaluation component of tasks 6.1 to 6.5 to assess human toxicity and ecotoxicity impacts from pesticide emissions. Further information and supporting references can be found at <http://usetox.org>.

Table 5. Chemical-specific input data for organic substances for USEtox

Parameter	Type	Symbol	Unit
Chemical abstract service registry number	TEXT	CAS RN	-
Chemical common name	TEXT	Name	-
Target class for pesticides	TEXT	PesticideTargetClass	-
Chemical class for pesticides	TEXT	PesticideChemClass	-
Molar mass	FLOAT	MW	g/mol
pKa chemical class	FLOAT	pKaChemClass	-
pKa base reaction	FLOAT	pKa.gain	-
pKa acid reaction	FLOAT	pKa.loss	-
Partitioning coefficient between <i>n</i> -octanol and water	FLOAT	Kow	l/l
Partitioning coefficient between organic carbon and water	FLOAT	Koc	l/kg
Henry's law constant (at 25°C)	FLOAT	K _{H25C}	Pa·m ³ /mol
Vapor pressure (at 25°C)	FLOAT	P _{vap25}	Pa
Solubility (at 25°C)	FLOAT	Sol ₂₅	mg/l
Partitioning coefficient between dissolved organic carbon and water	FLOAT	K _{DOC}	l/kg
Rate constant degradation in air	FLOAT	k _{degA}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in water	FLOAT	k _{degW}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in sediment	FLOAT	k _{degSd}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in soil	FLOAT	k _{degSl}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in above-ground plant tissues	FLOAT	k _{dissP}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in wheat	FLOAT	k _{dissWheat}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in rice	FLOAT	k _{dissRice}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in tomato	FLOAT	k _{dissTomato}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in apple	FLOAT	k _{dissApple}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in lettuce	FLOAT	k _{dissLettuce}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in potato	FLOAT	k _{dissPotato}	1/s

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Parameter	Type	Symbol	Unit
Bioaccumulation factor in plant roots	FLOAT	BAF _{root}	kg _{veg} /kg _{soil}
Bioaccumulation factor in plant leaves	FLOAT	BAF _{leaf}	kg _{veg} /kg _{soil}
Biotransfer factor in meat	FLOAT	BTF _{meat}	d/kg _{meat}
Biotransfer factor in milk	FLOAT	BTF _{milk}	d/kg _{milk}
Bioaccumulation factor in fish	FLOAT	BAF _{fish}	l/kg _{fish}
Average of the log of the species-specific geometric means of concentrations affecting 50% of the exposed species population for a defined endpoint	FLOAT	avlog _{EC50}	mg/l
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a non-cancer disease probability of 50% via inhalation	FLOAT	ED50 _{inh,noncanc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a non-cancer disease probability of 50% via ingestion	FLOAT	ED50 _{ing,noncanc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a cancer disease probability of 50% via inhalation	FLOAT	ED50 _{inh,canc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a cancer disease probability of 50% via ingestion	FLOAT	ED50 _{ing,canc}	kg/lifetime

Table 6. Chemical-specific input data for metal ions (available e.g. in copper fungicides) for USEtox

Parameter	Type	Symbol	Unit
Chemical abstract service registry number		CAS RN	-
Chemical common name		Name	-
Molar mass	FLOAT	MW	g/mol
pKa chemical class	FLOAT	pKaChemClass	-
pKa base reaction	FLOAT	pKa.gain	-
pKa acid reaction	FLOAT	pKa.loss	-
Partitioning coefficient between <i>n</i> -octanol and water	FLOAT	K _{ow}	l/l
Partitioning coefficient between organic carbon and water	FLOAT	K _{oc}	l/kg
Henry's law constant (at 25°C)	FLOAT	K _{H25C}	Pa·m ³ /mol
Vapor pressure (at 25°C)	FLOAT	P _{vap25}	Pa
Solubility (at 25°C)	FLOAT	Sol ₂₅	mg/l
Partitioning coefficient between dissolved organic carbon and water	FLOAT	K _{DOC}	l/kg
	FLOAT		
Partitioning coefficient between suspended solids and water	FLOAT	K _{pSS}	l/kg
Partitioning coefficient between sediment particles and water	FLOAT	K _{pSd}	l/kg
Partitioning coefficient between soil particles and water	FLOAT	K _{pSl}	l/kg
Rate constant degradation in air	FLOAT	k _{degA}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in water	FLOAT	k _{degW}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in sediment	FLOAT	k _{degSd}	1/s
Rate constant degradation in soil	FLOAT	k _{degSl}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in above-ground plant tissues	FLOAT	k _{dissP}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in wheat	FLOAT	k _{dissWheat}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in rice	FLOAT	k _{dissRice}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in tomato	FLOAT	k _{dissTomato}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in apple	FLOAT	k _{dissApple}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in lettuce	FLOAT	k _{dissLettuce}	1/s
Rate constant dissipation in potato	FLOAT	k _{dissPotato}	1/s
Bioaccumulation factor in plant roots	FLOAT	BAF _{root}	kg _{veg} /kg _{soil}
Bioaccumulation factor in plant leaves	FLOAT	BAF _{leaf}	kg _{veg} /kg _{soil}
Biotransfer factor in meat	FLOAT	BTF _{meat}	d/kg _{meat}
Biotransfer factor in milk	FLOAT	BTF _{milk}	d/kg _{milk}
Bioaccumulation factor in fish	FLOAT	BAF _{fish}	l/kg _{fish}

Parameter	Type	Symbol	Unit
Average of the log of the species-specific geometric means of concentrations affecting 50% of the exposed species population for a defined endpoint	FLOAT	avlog _{EC50}	mg/l
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a non-cancer disease probability of 50% via inhalation	FLOAT	ED50 _{inh,noncanc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a non-cancer disease probability of 50% via ingestion	FLOAT	ED50 _{ing,noncanc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a cancer disease probability of 50% via inhalation	FLOAT	ED50 _{inh,canc}	kg/lifetime
Human-equivalent lifetime dose per person that causes a cancer disease probability of 50% via ingestion	FLOAT	ED50 _{ing,canc}	kg/lifetime

4.1.4 dynamiCROP model data formats

In Table 7 and Table 8, an overview of the input data format requirements of the dynamiCROP model is given that is used in the environmental evaluation component of tasks 6.1 to 6.5 to assess plant uptake of pesticides and related human exposure and human health impacts. Further information and supporting references can be found at <http://dynamicrop.org>.

Table 7. Chemical-specific input data for organic substances for dynamiCROP

Parameter	Type	Description
CAS_RN	TEXT	US NLM ChemIDPlus (Chemical Abstracts Registry Number).
SUBSTANCE_NAME	TEXT	Common name for a substance.
TYPE_TARGET	TEXT	Type of substance with respect to target organism, such as herbicide, insecticide or metabolite.
TYPE_CHEMICAL	TEXT	Type of substance with respect to chemical class, such as sulfonylurea or aryloxyalkanoic acid.
MW	FLOAT	Molecular weight [g/mol] (Mass of 1 molecule relative to the unified atomic mass unit [u] (1/12 the carbon-12 isotope mass); molar mass [g/mol] = average molecular weight [u]).
MV	FLOAT	Molar volume [cm ³ /mol] = MW/ρM (ρM: mass density [g/cm ³] or [g/ml]). Only required for alternative calculation of solute mobility of formulation deposit in cuticular membrane.
Kaw	FLOAT	Air/water partition coefficient [(kg/m ³)/(kg/m ³): dimensionless Henry's law constant). Alternatively, the Henry's law constant, H, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only Kaw will be used.
H	FLOAT	Henry's law constant (at +25°C) [Pa*m ³ /mol]: $H = P^0 / (S_{H2O} / MW)$. Alternatively, the air/water partition coefficient, Kaw, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only Kaw will be used.
P ⁰	FLOAT	Saturation vapour pressure or equilibrium partial pressure at 25°C [Pa]: pressure at which a liquid is in equilibrium with its vapour (measure of the tendency to vapourise).
S _{H2O}	FLOAT	Water solubility (at 20°C) [g/m ³]: mass that can dissolve in a given volume of water. Note: may be pH sensitive for some substances.
Kow	FLOAT	<i>N</i> -octanol/water partition coefficient [(kg/m ³)/(kg/m ³)
Koc	FLOAT	Soil organic carbon/water partition coefficient [L/kg]: also known as »organic carbon soil sorption coefficient«, a measure of how well a substance adsorbs (sticks) to soil. If no value is specified, a linear Koc-Kow relation valid for »predominantly hydrophobics« will be applied.

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Parameter	Type	Description
$t_{1/2,air}$	FLOAT	Degradation half-life in air [d]: alternatively, the gas phase degradation rate constant, $k_{deg,air}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,air}$ will be used.
$k_{deg,air}$	FLOAT	Gas phase degradation rate constant (no particle degradation) [1/d]: alternatively, the half-life in air, $t_{1/2,air}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,air}$ will be used.
$t_{1/2,water}$	FLOAT	Degradation half-life in bulk water [d]: alternatively, the bulk water degradation rate constant, $k_{deg,water}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,water}$ will be used. Value is only use for paddy rice.
$k_{deg,water}$	FLOAT	Bulk water degradation rate constant [1/d]: alternatively, the half-life in bulk water, $t_{1/2,water}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,water}$ will be used. Value is only use for paddy rice.
$t_{1/2,soil}$	FLOAT	Degradation half-life in bulk soil [d]: alternatively, the bulk soil degradation rate constant, $k_{deg,soil}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,soil}$ will be used.
$k_{deg,soil}$	FLOAT	Buk soil degradation rate constant [1/d]: alternatively, the half-life in bulk soil, $t_{1/2,soil}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,soil}$ will be used.
$t_{1/2,plantsurface}$	FLOAT	Degradation half-life on plant surface [d]: alternatively, the plant surface degradation rate constant, $k_{deg,plantsurface}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,plantsurface}$ will be used. Note: if no information about degradation on plant surface is available, a correlation factor between plant surface and soil degradation will be applied.
$k_{deg,plantsurface}$	FLOAT	Plant surface degradation rate constant [1/d]: alternatively, the half-life on plant surface, $t_{1/2,plantsurface}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,plantsurface}$ will be used. Note: if no information about degradation on plant surface is available, a correlation factor between plant surface and soil degradation will be applied.
$t_{1/2,plant}$	FLOAT	Degradation half-life in plant (interior) [d]: alternatively, the plant degradation rate constant, $k_{deg,plant}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,plant}$ will be used. Note: if no information about degradation in plant is available, a correlation factor between plant interior and soil degradation will be applied.
$k_{deg,plant}$	FLOAT	Plant degradation rate constant [1/d]: alternatively, the half-life in plant (interior), $t_{1/2,plant}$, can be specified. Note: if both values are given, only $k_{deg,plant}$ will be used. Note: if no information about degradation in plant is available, a correlation factor between plant interior and soil degradation will be applied.
Medium _{metabolism}	TEXT	Medium, in which the substance generally metabolises. Note: used as information for running a metabolite instead of the parent substance in case the degradation half-life of the parent substance is too short for a model run.
fr_M _{metabolism}	FLOAT	Fraction of the parent substance that metabolises to metabolite (including name of the metabolite) [(kg/m ²)/(kg/m ²)]. Note: used as information for running a metabolite instead of the parent substance in case the degradation half-life of the parent substance is too short for a model run.

Table 8. Scenario input data for dynamiCROP

Parameter	Type	Description
TYPE_APPLICATION	TEXT	Formulation type and typical application medium (based on GDPF:2008a): Dustable Powder (DP): air; Emulsifiable Concentrate (EC) or Emulsion, Oil in Water (EW): air; Any other Liquid (AL) or Micro-Emulsion (ME): air; Wettable Powder (WP) or Suspension Concentrate (SC): air; Water-soluble Powder (SP): air; Granule (GR): paddy water. Note that this value varies between different agricultural produces and regions of interest.
MEDIUM_APPLICATION	TEXT	Method of substance application. air (spray); dust coating; soil (injection); soil (surface); water (add-on). Note that this value varies between different agricultural produces and regions of interest.
DATE_APPLICATION	DATE	Date [date] of substance application. Note that this value varies between different agricultural produces and regions of interest.
MASS_APPLICATION	FLOAT	Total mass [kg/m ²] of substance application per year. Note that this value varies between different agricultural produces and regions of interest.
MEDIUM_EMISSION	TEXT	Emission receiving medium.
MASS_EMISSION	FLOAT	Total continuous source or background mass [kg] of substance per year. Note that this value varies between different agricultural produces and regions of interest.

4.1.5 Economic data/models

Table 9 and Figure 7 provide an overview of data requirements for the empirical comparative analysis using FADN microdata and for the ex-ante assessment of pesticide use reduction strategies using a simulation model.

Table 9: Example of FADN data (summary statistics) used for economic impact assessments (Source: Grovermann et al., forthcoming)

	Class 1		Class 2		Class 3		Class 4	
Description	Dairy farming under cool conditions		Dairy farming under temperate conditions More intensive		Less intensive		Dairy farming under warm conditions	
Organic certified	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES
Farms (#)	4815	1066	20162	1029	9161	439	5116	115
Production data								
Production (kg/cow) ¹	6869.97 (2,064.61)	6282.22 (1,644.07)	7247.26 (1,656.14)	6285.68 (1,544.46)	5247.69 (1,552.40)	4601.19 (1,360.86)	6667.26 (2,105.79)	6039.61 (2,221.70)
Land (ha/cow)	2.13 (1.95)	2.70 (2.37)	1.09 (0.66)	1.31 (0.69)	1.01 (0.72)	1.59 (0.91)	0.65 (0.70)	1.11 (1.30)
Labor (days/cow)	0.06 (0.04)	0.06 (0.04)	0.02 (0.01)	0.03 (0.02)	0.07 (0.04)	0.09 (0.05)	0.04 (0.03)	0.04 (0.02)
Plant protection costs (€/cow)	1104.73 (579.57)	951.83 (674.48)	770.33 (383.54)	790.32 (577.77)	447.08 (214.11)	307.69 (205.62)	1199.07 (560.71)	1187.01 (727.02)
Mach. costs (€/cow)	202.86 (163.14)	237.87 (194.22)	168.61 (101.47)	204.55 (120.95)	83.37 (66.85)	131.73 (114.63)	72.53 (75.68)	62.59 (73.05)
Other costs (€/cow)	323.84 (253.88)	351.91 (283.21)	363.39 (181.08)	391.71 (203.12)	110.37 (82.86)	131.24 (103.18)	183.17 (152.69)	147.14 (138.14)
Min. temperature (C)	2.30 (1.93)	2.45 (1.79)	6.37 (1.33)	5.95 (1.13)	4.61 (0.68)	4.54 (0.99)	9.43 (2.50)	10.40 (2.00)
Max. temperature (C)	9.88	10.47	13.86	13.44	12.59	12.92	19.10	19.70

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

	Class 1		Class 2		Class 3		Class 4	
Description	Dairy farming under cool conditions		Dairy farming under temperate conditions More intensive		Less intensive		Dairy farming under warm conditions	
	(2.22)	(2.23)	(1.54)	(1.37)	(1.03)	(1.29)	(1.91)	(1.72)
Farm characteristics data								
Farm size (ha)	163.82 (369.82)	99.77 (151.09)	166.16 (359.01)	144.77 (244.58)	46.74 (149.01)	41.07 (59.79)	51.95 (186.30)	53.39 (50.98)
Econ. Size (ESU)	196.54 (372.01)	126.08 (160.49)	374.90 (604.28)	323.73 (381.42)	65.07 (133.67)	57.54 (68.32)	205.00 (324.86)	179.72 (158.36)
Stocking d. (cows/ha)	1.17 (1.50)	0.90 (0.44)	2.13 (1.72)	1.44 (0.45)	2.12 (1.82)	1.23 (0.52)	8.30 (55.34)	3.03 (2.61)
Subsidies (€/ha)	318.94 (362.61)	254.07 (165.52)	346.52 (153.42)	302.88 (95.21)	205.84 (174.10)	252.90 (103.06)	1119.49 (7,227.97)	432.06 (468.69)
Assets (€)	1782.69 (1,460.61)	2162.21 (1,562.04)	1288.69 (926.35)	1700.11 (1,149.22)	1542.28 (1,169.87)	1885.41 (1,602.62)	808.71 (877.94)	679.03 (741.99)
Forage area (ha)	116.68 (235.26)	85.16 (121.89)	103.43 (175.18)	112.46 (171.01)	27.46 (83.71)	31.34 (43.85)	35.50 (78.35)	48.09 (48.84)
Specialization (prop.)	0.65 (0.14)	0.61 (0.14)	0.68 (0.16)	0.69 (0.14)	0.62 (0.16)	0.59 (0.14)	0.72 (0.15)	0.67 (0.15)
Family labor (prop.)	0.81 (0.31)	0.89 (0.22)	0.86 (0.26)	0.82 (0.25)	0.96 (0.14)	0.95 (0.17)	0.90 (0.21)	0.84 (0.26)
Renting land (Y/N)	0.88 (0.32)	0.85 (0.36)	0.94 (0.24)	0.95 (0.22)	0.72 (0.45)	0.71 (0.45)	0.75 (0.44)	0.64 (0.48)
Less favored (Y/N)	163.82 (369.82)	99.77 (151.09)	166.16 (359.01)	144.77 (244.58)	46.74 (149.01)	41.07 (59.79)	51.95 (186.30)	53.39 (50.98)
Fallow (Y/N)	0.03 (0.19)	0.05 (0.21)	0.08 (0.29)	0.11 (0.33)	0.03 (0.25)	0.08 (0.27)	0.05 (0.22)	0.08 (0.43)

Figure 8: Dynamics of an agent-based optimisation model for assessing the impact of pesticide use reduction strategies (Source: Grovermann et al., 2017)

5 Data storage and data protection

All existing data described in the present milestone are available in public repositories. Relevant datasets that will be made available by project partners are shared on the SPRINT Nextcloud repository (SPRINT-data.eu) hosted by Netcup (Germany). The database will be secured against unauthorised access by means of a password-protected login process. Different user groups will be created to regulate who is able to view and edit data. The project data repository and maintenance of the database will be done by two SPRINT data managers. They will safeguard the data quality, set up required infrastructure for storage and backup, and facilitate data archiving and data sharing.

All personal data collected in the CSS will be pseudonymised before any treatment by replacing participant names with a code and protecting all electronic and paper records from unauthorised access (only designated researchers have access to these data). All results will be reported in a strictly non-identifiable format to protect the privacy of every subject. Personally identifiable information will be deleted after completion of the study. The handling of personal data complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the national legislation on data protection requirements in the country of the CSS.

Existing data collected for this project by DTU researchers are stored on the main drive at the contributing person(s)' laptop(s) and backed up at the DTU departments shared drive as per default DTU security settings. Locally stored data can be accessed only by laptop owner and data backed up at the departments shared drive can be accessed as organized by the department's IT structure. Data used or generated by DTU within this project are not affected by any ethical aspects. DTU researchers working on the project follow the Danish Conduct for Research Integrity and DTU's Policy of the Retention of Primary Material. The existing data collected by DTU do not contain any personal data that fall under the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), and no external data processor is used for any of the project-related data.

FiBL staff handles the data collected in the project with care. The data will be stored on a secured local server in Switzerland. FiBL has a set of TOMs in place to guarantee data security that are reviewed and updated regularly (at least once per year) including a set of measures for physical access control, system access control, storage control, transmission control, separation control, entry control and availability control. These include firewalls, DDos, RAID, logging, user identification, uninterruptible power supply, protection of server rooms etc. FiBL has an established Backup concept, Backups are taken every night on a 2nd server, which is kept 14 days. Additionally, there is a Weekly Backup on Tape to a third-party location outside the server room. The tapes are Encrypted. Only IT-Staff has access to the Backup.

6 References

Arena, M., Auteri, D., Barmaz, S., Brancato, A., Brocca, D., Bura, L., Carrasco Cabrera, L., Chiusolo, A., Civitella, C., Court Marques, D., et al., 2018. Peer review of the pesticide risk assessment of the active substance cypermethrin. EFSA Journal 16, e05402. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5402.

Dijkman, T.J., Birkved, M., Hauschild, M.Z., 2012. PestLCI 2.0: A second generation model for estimating emissions of pesticides from arable land in LCA. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 17, 973-986. doi:10.1007/s11367-012-0439-2.

Dorne, J.L., Richardson, J., Kass, G., Georgiadis, N., Monguidi, M., Pasinato, L., Cappe, S., Verhagen, H., Robinson, T., 2017. OpenFoodTox: EFSA's open source toxicological database on chemical hazards in food and feed. *EFSA Journal* 15, e15011. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2017.e15011.

Dorne, J.L.C.M., Richardson, J., Livaniou, A., Carnesecchi, E., Ceriani, L., Baldin, R., Kovarich, S., Pavan, M., Saouter, E., Biganzoli, F., et al., 2021. EFSA's OpenFoodTox: An open source toxicological database on chemicals in food and feed and its future developments. *Environment International* 146, 106293. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2020.106293.

Fantke, P., Aurisano, N., Provoost, J., Karamertzanis, P.G., Hauschild, M., 2020. Toward effective use of REACH data for science and policy. *Environment International* 135, 105336. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2019.105336.

Fantke, P., Charles, R., de Alencastro, L.F., Friedrich, R., Jolliet, O., 2011a. Plant uptake of pesticides and human health: Dynamic modeling of residues in wheat and ingestion intake. *Chemosphere* 85, 1639-1647. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2011.08.030.

Fantke, P., Chiu, W.A., Aylward, L., Judson, R., Huang, L., Jang, S., Guin, T., Rhomberg, L., Aurisano, N., McKone, T., Jolliet, O., 2021. Exposure and toxicity characterization of chemical emissions and chemicals in products: Global recommendations and implementation in USEtox. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 26, 899-915. doi:10.1007/s11367-021-01889-y.

Fantke, P., Jolliet, O., 2016. Life cycle human health impacts of 875 pesticides. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 21, 722-733. doi:10.1007/s11367-015-0910-y.

Fantke, P., Juraske, R., Antón, A., Friedrich, R., Jolliet, O., 2011b. Dynamic multicrop model to characterize impacts of pesticides in food. *Environmental Science and Technology* 45, 8842-8849. doi:10.1021/es201989d.

Gentil, C., Basset-Mens, C., Manteaux, S., Mottes, C., Maillard, E., Biard, Y., Fantke, P., 2020. Coupling pesticide emission and toxicity characterization models for LCA: Application to open-field tomato production in Martinique. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 227, 124099. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124099.

Grovermann, C., Quiédeville, S., Muller, A., Leiber, F., Moakes, S., forthcoming: Does organic certification make economic sense for dairy farmers in Europe? - A latent class counterfactual analysis. *Agricultural Economics*.

Grovermann, C., Schreinemachers, P., Berger, T., 2017: 'Smart' policies to reduce pesticide use and avoid income trade-offs: An agent-based model applied to Thai agriculture. *Ecological Economics*, 132, 91-103.

Henderson, A.D., Hauschild, M.Z., van de Meent, D., Huijbregts, M.A.J., Larsen, H.F., Margni, M., McKone, T.E., Payet, J., Rosenbaum, R.K., Jolliet, O., 2011. USEtox fate and ecotoxicity factors for comparative assessment of toxic emissions in life cycle analysis: Sensitivity to key chemical properties. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 16, 701-709. doi:10.1007/s11367-011-0294-6.

Renaud-Gentié, C.,

Dijkman, T.J., Bjørn, A., Birkved, M., 2015. Pesticide emission modelling and freshwater ecotoxicity assessment for Grapevine LCA: Adaptation of PestLCI 2.0 to viticulture. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 20, 1528-1543. doi:10.1007/s11367-015-0949-9.

Rosenbaum, R.K., Bachmann, T.M., Gold, L.S., Huijbregts, M.A.J., Jolliet, O., Juraske, R., Koehler, A., Larsen, H.F., MacLeod, M., Margni, M.D., McKone, T.E., Payet, J., Schuhmacher, M., van de Meent, D., Hauschild, M.Z., 2008. USEtox - The UNEP-SETAC toxicity model: Recommended characterisation factors for human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity in life cycle impact assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 13, 532-546. doi:10.1007/s11367-008-0038-4.

Rosenbaum, R.K., Huijbregts, M.A.J., Henderson, A.D., Margni, M., McKone, T.E., van de Meent, D., Hauschild, M.Z., Shaked, S., Li, D.S., Gold, L.S., Jolliet, O., 2011. USEtox human exposure and toxicity factors for comparative assessment of toxic emissions in life cycle analysis: Sensitivity to key chemical properties. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 16, 710-727. doi:10.1007/s11367-011-0316-4.

Williams, A.J., Grulke, C.M., Edwards, J., McEachran, A.D., Mansouri, K., Baker, N.C., Patlewicz, G., Shah, I., Wambaugh, J.F., Judson, R.S., Richard, A.M., 2017. The CompTox Chemistry Dashboard: A community data resource for environmental chemistry. *Journal of Cheminformatics* 9, 61. doi:10.1186/s13321-017-0247-6.